

Deliverable 7.4

Project leaflet and other materials

Work package	WP7: Communication, dissemination, and future engagement
Lead- beneficiary	EUFIC
WP Leader	EUFIC
Relevant Task	T7.4
Participants	All Partners
Dissemination Level	Public
Due Date (month)	M36

Document History and Information

VERSION	DATE	DESCRIPTION AND COMMENTS	AUTHOR
0.1	21 October 2020	First draft	Iva Doric, Raymond Gemen
	21 October 2020	Feedback	Mads Dahl Gjefsen
	21 October 2020	Feedback	Matthieu Flourakis
0.2	23 October 2020	Second draft	Iva Doric, Raymond Gemen
	25 October 2020	Feedback	Jacqueline Broerse
1.0	26 October 2020	Final version	Iva Doric, Raymond Gemen

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Deliverable 7.4 – Project leaflet and other materials

1. Introduction

This report outlines the development and production of tailored dissemination materials, which were developed as part of Deliverable 7.4 “*Project leaflet and other materials*” under Work Package 7 (WP7). Due to the complex nature of the project and the wide variety of actors and stakeholders it aims to reach and engage, tailored dissemination is crucial; e.g. a one-pager to communicate policy recommendations to high-level policy actors is very different from a webinar laying out the food systems challenges to a wider audience. Therefore, various dissemination materials were created, including among others a project leaflet (booklet), roll-up for physical meetings, press releases, website content, E-newsletters, social media messages, policy recommendation, audio-visual materials, a scientific article, an infographic, progress articles and a conference booklet. Besides the materials that have already been completed, this report also highlights the plans for dissemination materials that are yet to be released. This deliverable is linked to Task 7.4 “*Development and production of tailored dissemination materials*”.

The aim of this deliverable is to provide an overview of the project’s communication and dissemination materials developed throughout the FIT4FOOD2030 project. EUFIC has worked with all project partners to develop, tailor, and target the communication materials for efficient dissemination, communication, and exploitation of FIT4FOOD2030 outputs.

2. Purpose

The FIT4FOOD2030 project supports the implementation of the European Commission’s FOOD 2030 research and innovation (R&I) policy framework, emphasizing the need for double transformation of both food system and R&I practices (European Union 2018). To achieve its goals, the FIT4FOOD2030 project has brought together several different food system actors at the level of cities, regions, countries, and Europe. Along with that, the goal of FIT4FOOD2030 is to disseminate information to the wider audiences. Considering the diversity of stakeholders involved in the project, it was necessary to create various materials for communication and dissemination of project’s activities and outcomes. Therefore, the aims of the communication and dissemination materials are to ensure information about the project’s objectives and results are effectively disseminated to relevant audiences and to promote the use of results from the project.

3. Dissemination materials

The design of dissemination materials was based on the previously developed FIT4FOOD2030 visual identity described in Deliverable 7.3 “*Project identity and website*”. Some of the materials were intended for printing and physical distribution, but most of them were distributed via distinct digital channels.

Table 1. Summary of the FIT4FOOD2030 dissemination materials

Type of Dissemination Material	Purpose and reach (if available)	Audience
Leaflet	Provide general information about the project; can be used as a bookmark or roll-up Reach: 2,000 printed	Citizens and consumers, CSOs, school children and students, knowledge and education centres, policy makers, businesses, non-governmental organisations, funding agencies
Roll-up	Draw attention to the project at events and conferences; explain the FOOD 2030 Platform; designed specifically for the High-Level meeting	Participants of the High-Level meeting on World Food Day, on 16 October 2019
Press Release	Raise visibility of the project; explain different ways FIT4FOOD2030 aims to use innovation to make the European food system future-proof	Citizens and consumers, CSOs, knowledge and education centres, policy makers, businesses, non-governmental organisations, funding agencies
Official Website	Reach out to a broad range of stakeholders; one place to showcase all project's activities Reach: 22,177 users	Citizens and consumers, CSOs, school children and students, knowledge and education centres, policy makers, businesses, non-governmental organisations, funding agencies
E-Newsletter	Regularly spread insights, initiatives, events, and ideas beyond the FIT4FOOD2030 official website; encourage stakeholders to engage in various ways Reach: 557 subscribers	Citizens and consumers, CSOs, students, knowledge and education centres, policy makers, businesses, non-governmental organisations, funding agencies
Social Media	Disseminate information about FIT4FOOD2030 to a broad range of audiences Reach: 449,473 impressions of 118 Twitter posts	Citizens and consumers, CSOs, students, knowledge and education centres, policy makers, businesses, non-governmental organisations, funding agencies
Trend Cards	A tool that can be used in interactive sessions or as an ice-breaker to connect and engage in conversations on different topics relevant to the food system, such as drivers, barriers and the challenges they create within the	Citizens and consumers, CSOs, school children and students, knowledge and education centres, policy makers, businesses, non-governmental organisations, funding agencies

	food and nutrition system as well as for research and innovation	
Policy Recommendations one-pager	Concisely written policy advice prepared for a group interested in three necessary revisions to R&I funding systems that also has the authority to make decisions	Policy makers, funding organisations, research institutions
Video Interviews	Explaining different activities within the project; pointing out important aspects of food system transformation and need for responsible research and innovation practices; promoting the final conference and Sustainable Food Systems Network	Citizens and consumers, CSOs, school children and students, knowledge and education centres, policy makers, businesses, non-governmental organisations, funding agencies
Webinars	Amplify the outreach to relevant audiences and disseminate specific project outputs and activities	Knowledge and education centres, policy makers, businesses, non-governmental organisations, funding agencies
Additional Dissemination Materials About the Project's Progress	Inform about FIT4FOOD2030's progress	Citizens and consumers, CSOs, school children and students, knowledge and education centres, policy makers, businesses, non-governmental organisations, funding agencies
Bioblogs Booklet	For the 2 nd High-Level FOOD 2030 conference organised in Plovdiv in 2018	High-Level conference participants
Infographic	Provide a brief summary of the project's aims, results and future perspectives to engage within the transformation endeavor of both the food system and research and innovation (R&I)	Citizens and consumers, CSOs, school children and students, knowledge and education centres, policy makers, businesses, non-governmental organisations, funding agencies
Nutrition Bulletin Article	Provide the overview of the FIT4FOOD2030 project	Dietitians and nutritionists

3.1. Leaflet

The FIT4FOOD2030 leaflet was the dissemination material developed first. It was developed and released at the end of 2018 as a bookmark which provided general information about the project. The bookmark (Figure 1) contained logo, one-sentence project description, official website address, hashtag, logos of the coordinator and partners, and funding disclaimer. The bookmark was printed and 2000 copies were distributed. Each partner was provided with 100 or 200 bookmarks to distribute through their networks and at conferences and events. The project bookmark was earlier made available to all project partners via Edugroepen (extranet).

FIT4FOOD2030

Towards FOOD 2030 – future-proofing the European food systems through Research & Innovation

A bookmark is a general dissemination material which primarily aims to facilitate building the “FIT4FOOD2030 brand” and increasing its visibility. An important advantage of a bookmark is its small size and practical dissemination. Stakeholders can easily pick it up at conferences and events or insert them into conference bags. The FIT4FOOD2030 leaflet could also be printed and used as a roll-up for events.

Figure 1. FIT4FOOD2030 bookmark (front and back side)

3.2. Roll-Up

Roll-ups are a practical and attractive way to draw attention to the project at events and conferences. Aside from already mentioned FIT4FOOD2030 leaflet that can also be used as a roll-up, another FIT4FOOD2030 roll-up was designed specifically for the High-Level meeting on World Food Day, on 16 October 2019 (Figure 2). It aimed primarily to explain the FOOD 2030 Platform (City and Food Labs, Policy Labs, and the EU Think Tank) as a key part of the project. Along with the FIT4FOOD2030 logo, hashtags, visual representation of the FOOD 2030 Platform and funding disclaimer, the roll-up contained an interactive map on which all the European countries that took part in the project were highlighted.

fit4food2030.eu - #FOOD2030EU

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No774088

Figure 2. FIT4FOOD2030 roll-up designed for and used on World Food Day 2019

3.3. Press Release

Appearing on the media is considered as a key activity to reach many groups of targeted stakeholders. Therefore, a press release *“The food system is not ready for the future: how can innovation help?”* was released on 21st November 2018 (Figure 3). The press release explained different ways the project aims to use innovation to make the European food system future-proof. The press release was submitted to the European database ‘AlphaGalileo’ and distributed among all project partners, including their colleagues responsible for communication. ‘AlphaGalileo’ is online resource of scientific news for journalists which supports communication between researchers, journalists and the public. AlphaGalileo is ensuring media coverage of research. The press-release was also re-published by EUFIC (Figure 4) and on the Agrifood LCA LAB’s website (Figure 5) allowing for a bigger reach.

fit4food2030.eu - #FOOD2030EU

Press release

The food system is not ready for the future: how can innovation help?

In short

- The European food system is NOT ready for the future.
- FIT4FOOD2030 (EU funded project) looks at how Research & Innovation can prepare the food system for the future.
- The FOOD 2030 Platform connects stakeholders at a European, national and local level, and will 1) help policy makers and ministries dealing with the food system to align Research & Innovation programmes and 2) build skills and knowledge among current and future researchers, entrepreneurs, policy-makers, and the society at large to enable change.

The new FOOD 2030 Platform connects European, national and local stakeholders to help policy/decision makers and researchers to improve their Research & Innovation programmes and build skills and knowledge across the different sectors and populations for a future-proof European food system.

Video

Prof Jacqueline Broerse explaining how FIT4FOOD203 will contribute to making the European food system future-proof: <https://youtu.be/z7RjVldXs0>.

The FOOD 2030 Platform

The current European food system is not ready for the future; the way of producing, processing, transporting, consuming and wasting food is not sustainable, particularly if it is to provide food and nutrition security for our future generations.

Transforming the food system towards a system that uses resources more efficiently, provides enough and nutritious food in a sustainable manner, and one that empowers communities that embrace the change, will be key.

In this context, the EU-funded FIT4FOOD2030 projects seeks to find ways to facilitate and accelerate this change by taking a 'food system approach', considering all processes and actors involved in the entire value chain; from inputs, to primary production (agriculture, aquaculture and fisheries), harvesting, storage, processing, packing, distribution, waste streams to consumer intake and back.

Another essential element in the FIT4FOOD2030 approach is 'Responsible Research & Innovation' (RRI). RRI is a dynamic process where all stakeholders involved in the Research & Innovation (R&I) practice come together to align and move towards desirable, sustainable and acceptable future outcomes.

The FIT4FOOD2030 project has established the 'FOOD 2030 Platform', which connects stakeholders at a European, national and local level to inform Research & Innovation programmes that are related to the food system. The Platform consists of three components;

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Figure 3. Press release *"The food system is not ready for the future: how can innovation help?"*

fit4food2030.eu - #FOOD2030EU

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No774088

The food system is not ready for the future: how can innovation help?

26 November 2018

In short

- The European food system is NOT ready for the future.
- FIT4FOOD2030 (EU funded project) looks at how Research & Innovation can prepare the food system for the future.
- The FOOD 2030 Platform connects stakeholders at a European, national and local level, and will 1) help policy makers and ministries dealing with the food system to align Research & Innovation programmes and 2) build skills and knowledge among current and future researchers, entrepreneurs, policy-makers, and the society at large to enable change.

The new FOOD 2030 Platform connects European, national and local stakeholders to help policy/decision makers and researchers to improve their Research & Innovation programmes and build skills and knowledge across the different sectors and populations for a future-proof European food system.

You may also like...

(FIT4FOOD2030)

Fostering Integration and Transformation for FOOD 2030

Schelkle

The Milan Urban Food Policy Pact and Mayors Summit: Dr Bettina

diets

CIRCLES kick-starts: from research on microbes to healthy

Sign up to our newsletter

Figure 4. Press release on EUFIC’s website

ENTI, FOOD, NEWS, STUDIO

THE FOOD SYSTEM IS NOT READY FOR THE FUTURE: HOW CAN INNOVATION HELP?

29/12/2018 AMMINISTRATORE

The European food system is NOT ready for the future. **FIT4FOOD2030 (EU funded project)** looks at how Research & Innovation can prepare the foodsystem for the future. The **FOOD 2030 Platform** connects stakeholders at a European, national and local level, and will:

1. help policy makers and ministries dealing with the food system to align Research & Innovation programmes and
2. build skills and knowledge among current and future researchers, entrepreneurs, policy-makers, and the society at large to enable change.

The new FOOD 2030 Platform connects European, national and local stakeholders to help policy/decision makers and researchers to improve their Research & Innovation programmes and build skills and knowledge across the different sectors and populations for a future-proof European food system.

Figure 5. Press release on Agrifood LCA LAB’s website

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3.4. Official Website

One of the project’s key dissemination platforms was FIT4FOOD2030 website (<https://fit4food2030.eu/>; Figure 6). To reach out to a broad range of stakeholders, a website dedicated to the FIT4FOOD2030 project was released soon after the project’s beginning. A temporary website which did not include characteristic FIT4FOOD2030 visuals went live on 12th December 2017. After incorporating the FIT4FOOD2030 graphic identity and FOOD 2030 Platform, the updated website went live on 17th April 2018.

FIT4FOOD2030 website is the main hub for information about the project targeted to all potential stakeholders. FIT4FOOD2030 website further aims to engage key stakeholders and preserve and promote the food systems approach and responsible research and innovation in the food system transformation. It was updated continuously throughout the project lifetime with input from all partners. The website will also be maintained for at least three years beyond the project’s ending.

Figure 6. Overview of the FIT4FOOD2030 official website

Besides giving a detailed overview of the project’s objectives and methods, throughout the project EUFIC continuously updated the website with news and event highlights, newsletter articles, reports and publications, webinars, other videos, and different tools that came out of the project. An insight into website analytics is presented in the Section 4. Impact, outreach & sustainability.

A special webpage dedicated to the recent project’s activities and other news related to food system sustainability was created on the FIT4FOOD2030 website and placed as a submenu item titled “News Items” (Figure 7). News Items (<https://fit4food2030.eu/category/news-items/>) were regularly updated with the help of FIT4FOOD2030 partners. There are currently (15th October 2020) 70 News Items published on the website. All News Items are created with a purpose to highlight specific activities, publications, events, other dissemination materials, etc. Overview of the News Items timeline on the webpage is displayed in Figure 8.

Figure 7. News Items as a submenu item on the FIT4FOOD2030 website

Figure 8. News Items timeline

3.5. E-newsletter

E-newsletters are a powerful tool to regularly spread insights, initiatives, events, and ideas beyond the FIT4FOOD2030 official website. Newsletters were prepared and sent through the Mailchimp platform. Their intent is to additionally encourage stakeholders to engage in various ways. At the beginning, newsletter audience consisted of the FOOD2030 Platform members. However, other interested stakeholders could subscribe to the FIT4FOOD2030 Newsletter by inserting their e-mail addresses in the sign-up box on the website (Figure 9). FIT4FOOD2030 Newsletter audience now counts 557 subscribers (15th October 2020).

Figure 9. Newsletter subscription form

Six newsletters were planned to be sent across the project’s lifetime. Currently, already seven newsletters have been sent out (Figure 12), and the last one will be sent in December 2020. To increase the newsletter’s reach and invite new subscribers, newsletters were promoted on Twitter account @SciFoodHealth (Figure 10) and published on the FIT4FOOD2030 website (Figure 11). Since all newsletters are published on [the FIT4FOOD2030 official website](https://www.fit4food2030.eu), they can be easily accessed.

Newsletters focused on disseminating information about:

- Upcoming and past events,
- News regarding Food and City Labs, Policy Labs, and the EU Think Tank,
- Documents and publications,
- Calls for action and providing feedback (e.g. surveys).

Figure 10. Promotion of the newsletter on Twitter

FIT4FOOD2030

Towards FOOD 2030 – future-proofing the European food systems through Research & Innovation

Figure 11. Newsletters published on the FIT4FOOD2030 website

Figure 12. In total 7 newsletters have been distributed so far

fit4food2030.eu - #FOOD2030EU

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3.6. Social Media

Social media provides an easily accessible channel to disseminate information to a broad range of audiences. There are many social media platforms available online. For the FIT4FOOD2030 project communication and dissemination purposes, it was decided not to open new social media account(s) but rather to utilise existing EUFIC-managed Twitter account [@SciFoodHealth](#) dedicated to news on food and health EU-research collaborations that receive funding from the Horizon 2020 Framework Programme, since its audience counts over 22 thousand followers.

Twitter is an attractive platform as it gathers a broad audience base, including the general public, researchers, policy makers and other important stakeholders involved in the food system transformation. Partners were also encouraged to use their personal and institution accounts to further outreach. Two hashtags were used across the project’s related messages; The European Commission’s Food 2030 team already started using [#FOOD2030EU](#) to promote the implementation of their FOOD 2030 Policy Framework, which was thankfully being pick up and built upon, as well as a project specific one: [#FIT4FOOD2030](#).

Twitter was used for the dissemination of relevant information from the project and the project’s partners (Figure 13). Detailed Twitter analytics is described in the Section 4. Impact, outreach & sustainability.

Figure 13. Examples of Twitter posts on [@SciFoodHealth](#)

3.7. Trend Cards

Trends represent drivers and barriers affecting the food system and its transformation. FIT4FOOD2030 aimed to reach a wide range of stakeholders and encourage the dialogue about both the food system and R&I transformation. To overcome the challenge of engaging about the same topic on multiple levels, [the card game Trends in the Food System](#) was developed based on the Task 2.1 “*Analysis of visions, trends, drivers and barriers of the food systems and food and nutrition security R&I*”. It serves as a tool that can be used in interactive sessions or as an ice-breaker to connect and engage in conversations on different topics relevant to the food system, such as drivers, barriers and the challenges they create within the food and nutrition system as well as for research and innovation. They were uploaded to the FIT4FOOD2030 website and open for anyone to print and use freely.

Trends card game contains 60 cards with front and back side (Figure 14). The front side gives a brief overview of a specific trend, while the back side is intended for the notes.

Trends are divided in several categories and can be distinguished by the title situated in the top right corner of each card. These categories are:

- Megatrends,
- Agricultural production,
- Food processing,
- Consumer trends,
- Market economy, retail and logistics,
- Packaging and waste,
- Policy and other trends.

Figure 14. Trends card game – front and back side of one card

3.8. Policy Recommendations one-pager

A policy recommendation is concisely written policy advice prepared for some group that has the authority to make decisions. Three policy recommendations for research and innovation based on the Task 4.3 “*Forward outlook towards a food system transformation*” were developed for and disseminated at the High-Level meeting on 16 October 2019. It was published on the website (Figure 15) in November 2019. This document outlines three revisions to R&I funding systems and are relevant for R&I policy actors, funding organisations and research institutions.

Figure 16. Video interviews with members of the Advisory Board and the EU Think Tank

3.10. Webinars

As a part of the Task 7.2 “Development and implementation of multi-level stakeholder engagement plan” 4-webinar series was developed with an aim to amplify the outreach to relevant audiences and disseminate specific project outputs and activities. The webinar series is called “Towards sustainable food systems through Research and Innovation”. The process of developing these webinars is described in detail in the Deliverable 7.2 “Stakeholder Engagement Plan”.

The webinar series was recorded and additionally published on the [FIT4FOOD2030 official website](#) (Figure 17). Besides that, the webinars were translated into 4 individual Tools for Transformation that are located in the dynamic and interactive repository of tools, [the Knowledge Hub](#) (Figure 18).

Figure 17. Webinars are located on the FIT4FOOD2030 website

fit4food2030.eu - #FOOD2030EU

The focus of the webinars was on providing an overview of the food system challenges in relation to the different target audiences of each webinar. The aim was to increase visibility and awareness of the project, the FOOD 2030 policy framework and FOOD 2030 Platform, advocate for responsible research and innovation (RRI) and systems thinking for food system transformation, and to enhance the visibility and impact of specific project outputs. Along with that, each webinar contains a call to action to join the community of practice (developed under Task 7.6), which will provide stakeholders with a platform for two-way interaction, where discussion groups can be established, resources shared, and outputs from the FIT4FOOD project can be made visible and available.

The webinars took place during 2020:

- The first webinar “[Responsible Research and Innovation in the food systems](#)” on 10th March 2020,
- The second webinar “[Cities as change agents: building competences for future food systems](#)” on 3rd June 2020,
- The third webinar “[Transforming our food systems: Research and Innovation as an enabler of the Farm to Fork Strategy](#)” on 9th June 2020,
- The fourth webinar “[Responsible Research and Innovation \(RRI\) in policy making for future-proof food Systems](#)” on 14th July 2020.

Figure 18. Webinars as Communication Tools in the Knowledge Hub

3.11. Additional Dissemination Materials About the Project’s Progress

Three 2-4-page documents (Figure 19) were released as an additional dissemination material during the project’s duration. Their intent was to inform about FIT4FOOD2030’s progress. Therefore, an initial 2-page document as an introduction to the project was published in November 2018. In the document was given a brief overview of the project. One year into the project, another document was released. In January 2019, a three-pager with an intention to provide an overview of the project achievements at that point in time was published. Finally, FIT4FOOD2030 mid-term report summary was published in June 2019.

All dissemination materials mentioned above are available on the official FIT4FOOD2030 website, in the [“Reports & Publications”](#) section.

Figure 19. Overview of the FIT4FOOD2030 2-3-4-pagers

3.12. Bioblogs Booklet

For the 2nd High-Level FOOD 2030 conference organised in Plovdiv (Bulgaria) during 2018, a booklet was created. It contains a list of the speakers, their images, and biographies. The goal of the 2nd High-Level conference was to engage a wide diversity of actors in building a shared and inclusive vision and provide input to strategic long-term Food and Nutrition Security related R&I developments at the EU level. The creation of the Bioblogs booklet was a special request from the EU Commission. The content was provided beforehand, so EUFIC was responsible only for the booklet’s design (Figure 20).

Figure 20. A cover of the Bioblogs booklet

3.13. Infographic

Infographics are visually attractive tool for communication and engagement with a various audience. Therefore, to support the dissemination of the FIT4FOOD2030 project’s outcomes EUFIC in a collaboration with a graphic designer aims to create the infographic that will provide a brief summary of the project’s aims, results and future perspectives to engage within the transformation endeavor of both the food system and research and innovation (R&I).

The infographic will focus on:

- urgency of the European food system as well as R&I transformation,
- the scope of responsible research and innovation,
- stakeholder engagement opportunities (FOOD 2030 Platform and Sustainable Food Systems Network),
- and the repository of practical tools and guidelines that were developed during the project’s duration.

The infographic will be disseminated widely during November and December 2020. Some parts of the infographic will be incorporated in the FIT4FOOD2030 Nutrition Bulletin article.

Figure 20. Draft version of the FIT4FOOD2030 infographic

3.14. Nutrition Bulletin article

Nutrition Bulletin is the official scientific journal of the British Nutrition Foundation. It is an international, peer-reviewed journal that focuses on the recent developments in human nutrition science. FIT4FOOD2030 was offered an opportunity to contribute to the journal with a paper in the Emerging Research section. The articles within this section aim to provide the updates on new research projects funded by, for example, EU or UK research councils. The Emerging Research papers provide summary overviews of findings at the end of projects. The Emerging Research paper’s length is between 2,000-5,000 words, without abstract and references. The review process includes the Nutrition Bulletin Editorial Board but may also be reviewed by other experts in the field using a single-blind peer-reviewing process.

The Nutrition Bulletin FIT4FOOD2030 article will be centred around the practical, tangible outputs of the project, such as the Tools for Transformation and the Sustainable Food Systems Network, which will both be described in Deliverable 7.5. The article will be a combined effort of several colleagues

within the FIT4FOOD2030 project and will enable further dissemination of important aspects of the food system sustainability and responsible research and innovation practices. The target audience of the Nutrition Bulletin journal are dietitians and nutritionists, so this article will manage to draw their attention to the subject of sustainability. The paper is currently in progress and will be submitted to the journal by the end of October 2020.

4. Impact, outreach & sustainability

The impact, outreach and sustainability of the work covered by this Deliverable can be estimated by considering the available analytics for the social media and FIT4FOOD2030 website. They are presented in Table 2 and Table 3.

Since launching, the website has received 97,349 pageviews by 22,177 users, with 73,923 unique pageviews. When taken into account that half-way through the project FIT4FOOD2030 website gained more than 2 times less pageviews, it can be concluded that the project's visibility grew successfully with time and that the website was an important source of information about the FIT4FOOD2030 project. Even though the time visitors spent on the website has not significantly changed, traffic on the website grew more than 200 %, which justified all the effort and resources put into building it.

Table 2. Website Analytics for the FIT4FOOD2030 official website

Website Analytics			
	October 2017 - April 2019	October 2017 - October 2020	Comparison
Pageviews	31,237	97,349	↑ 212 %
Sessions	10,354	35,824	↑ 246 %
Users	6,626	22,177	↑ 235 %
Average session duration	2:46 min	2:44 min	↓ 1 %
Average time on page	1:22 min	1:34 min	↑ 15 %

Besides the official website, Twitter was an important digital communication and dissemination channel. Twitter analytics (Table 3) shows that there was an increase in number of Tweets and engagement with them as the time passed by. Posts that included two project's hashtags #FIT4FOOD2030 and #FOOD2030EU have achieved a significant reach. The overall number of posts, impressions and engagement has doubled. FIT4FOOD2030 has managed not only to communicate through the @SciFoodHealth account but also through other Twitter accounts, e.g. from partners and partner institutions. Therefore, since May 2019, 1920 Tweets were retweeted or posted by partners, partner institutions and others.

Table 3. Twitter social media analytics for #FIT4FOOD2030 and #FOOD2030EU

Twitter account analytics (@SciFoodHealth)			
	October 2017 – April 2019	October 2017 – October 2020	Comparison
Number of posts on @SciFoodHealth	58	118	↑ 103 %
Impressions ¹ (overall)	224,321	449,473	↑ 100 %
Average impressions/post	3,867	3,809	↓ 1 %
Engagement ² (overall)	3,390	7,720	↑ 128 %
Average Engagement/post	58	65	↑ 12 %

5. Reference(s)

European Union (2018) Recipe for change: An agenda for a climate-smart and sustainable food system for a healthy Europe, Report of the EC FOOD 2030 Independent Expert Group; ISBN 978-92-79-80356-7, doi: 10.2777/84024

¹ the number of times a Tweet appears to users in their timeline or search results

² the total number of times a user interacted with the Tweets

